

MOTIVATION APPROACH TO THE ORGANIZATION OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6885095>

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Abstract: *Innovative activity is continuous activity based on news. Therefore, the innovative approach is one of the main tools in the preschool education system. We decided to share our thoughts about this with you in this article.*

Key word: *Planning, organization, leadership, control, innovation, speech development, "First step"*

Аннотация: *Инновационная деятельность - это непрерывная деятельность, основанная на инновациях. Поэтому инновационный подход - один из ключевых инструментов в системе дошкольного образования. Мы решили поделиться с вами своими мыслями по этому поводу в этой статье.*

Ключевые слова: *планирование, организация, лидерство, контроль, инновации, развитие речи, «Первый шаг».*

Pre-school education is the initial part of continuous education. It ensures the formation of the child as a healthy and developed person, awakens his passion for learning and prepares him for systematic education. Preschool education up to 6-7 years old is carried out in state and non-state preschool educational institutions and in the family. The purpose of pre-school education is to prepare children for studying at school, to make the child a healthy, developed, independent person, to reveal his abilities, to educate his passion for reading and systematic education.

Protection of the life and health of children in a preschool educational institution is carried out by the preschool educational institution and state medical staff, as well as medical staff of the health authorities attached to the preschool educational institution.

Any innovation in the educational system cannot be an innovation. Therefore, it is necessary to point out the main differences between the concepts of "novation" and "innovation". For this, the exact form, content

and scope of the reform activity serve as the basis. If the activity is short-term and does not have the characteristics of a whole system, if it has set itself the task of changing only some elements of a certain system, then we are communicating with innovation. We can call innovation only if the activity is carried out on the basis of a certain conceptual approach and its result leads to the development of that system or its fundamental change. The criteria of both concepts are as follows: innovation is carried out within the framework of the current theory, limited in scope and time, methods are updated, and the result improves the previous system. Innovation will be systematic, integrated and continuous, it will design a new system of activity in a certain practice, completely update the positions of subjects of practice. In this way, new directions of activity are opened, new technologies are created, new qualitative results of activity are achieved, and as a result, the practice itself is renewed.

Implementation of innovation is carried out in innovation processes. Innovative process refers to the process of preparation for innovative changes and its implementation. The author also noted that innovative changes in the educational process, the introduction of any innovation into the educational system, is carried out directly by updating and changing the teacher's activity. By analyzing innovations in the educational system, their implementation, management of innovative processes, there was an opportunity to define the concept of innovative activity. Innovative activity is a force that moves, initiates and develops the pedagogical team. "Innovative activity is an activity aimed at solving complex problems that arise as a result of the incompatibility of traditional norms with new social requirements, or the conflict of the newly formed norm of practice with the existing norm," V.I. Slobadchikov says. Innovative activity is an important part of practice and theory, it is a system of actions of social subjects aimed at improving the qualities of a socio-cultural object, and it is not only the ability to solve problems in a certain area, but also having motivational training to solve problems in any situation. . The central issue of the teacher's innovative activity is the effective organization of the educational process.

Pedagogical technology is applied on the basis of a systematic approach to education and the age, mentality, outlook, knowledge, level of activity, purpose, direction, content, forms and methods of education are taken into account. The basis of the teacher's activity as an organizer and creator of this process is his knowledge and skills, his ability to influence the interest and aspirations of the child using technical means, and to

achieve guaranteed results by using methods that serve to activate the child.

As the times are rapidly changing, the field of education is changing along with it and requires the teacher to change his activities. The main task of a pedagogue is not only to teach, but also to manage, and it is necessary for him to properly organize and manage the educational process, to be able to continuously introduce innovations into the educational process, i.e., to carry out innovative activities. will be done.

Innovative activity is a force that motivates a pedagogue, increases his research ability, initiates and develops. Innovative activity is continuous activity based on innovations. It is formed and improved over a long period of time. The head of the organization is the main person in the organization and management of the innovative process in the preschool education organization. The task of the head of the organization is to plan, organize, manage and control the innovative process and ensure competitiveness among pedagogues.

Also, the head of the organization is required to analyze the activities of employees, determine the level of efficiency, and continuously develop innovation. We know that managing innovation processes is a unique challenge. In this process, the leader's initiative and management skills take a special place. The management of innovative processes in the educational system is carried out in 4 stages:

- Planning
- Organization
- Leadership
- Processes such as control.

If this consistency is fully implemented by the leader, the existing obstacles in the innovative activity in the educational process can be successfully solved.

Planning - is one of the forms of activity, defining educational strategies, what results are expected to be achieved in the future, educational efficiency, what actions should be taken for this, in what consistency and in what period, i.e. what, where and in what order should be implemented specifies that it should be increased. Activity planning means determining the purpose, composition, structure and deadlines of the work to be carried out in the future.

Organization of work - it is the process of determining who and what kind of work, obligations, rights, responsibilities, with whom and how to

interact, to decide the distribution, for the pedagogical team to work effectively together.

Leadership - due to the correct implementation of management planning and organization, it creates an opportunity to effectively unite the team in the preschool education organization.

The coordination of actions performed by the subject of management to maintain a comfortable social and psychological environment in the pedagogical team is called leadership.

Controlling - control of the day-to-day process in preschool educational organizations is entrusted to the head of the organization and experienced pedagogues.

In this regard, the ability of employees to organize innovative activities is monitored. Today, preschool education organizations are working on the basis of the "First Step" state curriculum, which was approved by the state on July 7, 2018. In accordance with the program, it is desirable to carry out training processes in junior, middle and senior school preparation groups on the basis of innovative activities. In this, the child's existing inquisitiveness, talent, creativity, and inventive abilities are formed. In the future, these children will become professionals in physics, astronomy, informatics, economics and other sciences. Interactive games and innovative activities will give a good result in outdoor nature introduction classes. Children will acquire new knowledge, skills and abilities in the heart of open nature.

Such innovative activities can be used to develop speech in short training sessions, during repeated physical exercises, musical education and literature, plot games, introduction to the world around us, speech development, elementary mathematics, making applications, drawing. application during learning will have a positive effect.

By organizing innovative activities in preschool educational organizations, favorable conditions are created for the comprehensive development of the child, taking into account the individual needs of the child. The child quickly learns the knowledge given through this activity.

The main type of activity of the child is the game, and showing and performing innovative activities together with the game will remain in his memory for a long time. The logical, action and emotional type of memory is also well developed. It is possible to teach and develop a child through the game, adapt to innovative activities. In this case, the child's creative development is clearly invisible. In the future, the child's interest in the second language will increase and he will have brief ideas about this language.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the successful solution of complex issues such as educating the young generation, who are the owners of our future, as well-rounded people and independent thinkers in the future, depends in many ways on the teacher's professional skills, knowledge, creativity, pedagogical and depends on the organization and management of the educational process using information communication technologies.

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